

THE DECLINE OF REGIONAL POLITICS AND THE RISE OF NATIONAL POLITICAL PARTIES IN MANIPUR

Abstract:

Initially, the National Political Party, the Indian National Congress (INC), demonstrated itself as a vibrant and influential political party since the operation of territorial councils in Manipur. In contrast, the BJP could not make a successful stride in its first three decades in Manipur. However, the BJP increased its momentum with the coming of the NDA government at the centre under the Prime Ministership of Narendra Modi. The rise of the BJP is concurrent with the decline of regional political parties, especially the MPP and the increasing fatigue felt by people for experiencing a prolonged fifteen-years continuous rule under the INC. The push for uncompromised territorial integrity of Manipur, solving the issues of illegal migrations, unemployment and push for infrastructure development, which were manifested in the BJP's manifesto of the 12th legislative assembly election, also paves the way for the rise of the BJP. Most importantly, the rise of the BJP in the state is associated with the ascendancy of the BJP at the centre in 2014 and the dominant political culture of the state, i.e it is better to have the same political party to form the government in the State which is forming government at the centre.

Keywords:

INC, BJP, MPP, illegal migration, unemployment, Political culture.

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INTRODUCTION;

The politics of Manipur, historically and traditionally, is characterised by its local political parties with a strong sense of unique ethnic and cultural identity. The state political landscape has undergone tremendous change over the past decades, marked by a gradual decline of one dominant regional political forces like strong Manipur People's Party (MPP) and decimation of Manipur State Congress Party (MSCP), Federal Party of Manipur (FPM) and the concurrent, steady rise of the Indian National Congress (INC) and Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) not only in Manipur but also in North East India, are being observed. This political shift has not been happened in a very short period of time, it is driven by the interplay of factors including the evolution of regional political aspiration and losing faith upon locals political parties, leaderships, dynamics of BJP strategic political manoeuvring using of social media, election manifesto, planning and other policies frameworks, ability to tap locals anxieties, national narratives and Hindu nationalism, agendas of Manipur and Northeast state of India, has long

been a crucial of political change, social upheaval and cultural transformation. Earlier, the BJP had no significant influence in North-East India. It has emerged as a dominant force not only in Assam but also in Manipur, Arunachal Pradesh, and Tripura. At the same time, people have significantly lost their faith in the Indian National Congress(INC) due to its prolonged rule over the country. Actually, the party can not influence people as it has not evolved new ideas and manifestos, which the party once had. On the other hand, MPP, which once upon a time represented the voice of the state's people, the regional political aspiration of Manipur, the movement for the demand of statehood and ethnic identity, has also lost its influence as it fails to secure even a single seat in the state legislative assembly election. However, it was MPP that formed the state government after attaining statehood status, Md. Alimudin was the first state chief minister of state after attaining statehood in 1972. However, it shows that the party has an inclusive political character in the state.

THE DECLINE OF REGIONAL POLITICAL PARTIES IN MANIPUR

Both electors and the elected have no clear ideas about the federal structure of the Indian Constitution. Therefore, people have a wrong conception in their minds that if the centre is with any political party, that same party should form a government in the state, otherwise there would be no funding and financial assistance from the centre. So, both political actors and voters have ignorance and the same feeling in the elections. State regional political parties have no manipulative or political tactics to convey political ideas or aspirations to the people. Therefore, there has been witnessing decline in regional political parties in North East India. But, Nagaland has a certain political character; the socialist movement had dominated Nagaland, manifested in the form of Naga insurgency, undermining their rights over them. And, people have no chance for their choice of their political rights over them. In Assam, the political scene was primarily divided among regional parties like Asom Gana Parishad (AGP) and Indian National Congress(INC). The famous Assam agitation, which took place from 1979 to 1985 against illegal immigration from Bangladesh, resulted in the signing of the Assam Accord in 1985, which directly led to the formation of Assam Gana Parishad (AGP). It was the regional political party formed out of the movement, and thus paved the way for the formation of a government by a regional political party with its full regional aspirations. Sometimes, we can mention the MPP of Manipur, which was the oldest regional political party to form a state government after attaining statehood status.

But, due to certain mistakes such as lust for power and self-contradiction and floor crossing, defections, change of new political party, lack of political ideologies, corruption and political jealousy rise among themselves. The lack of experience of the leaders and lust for power among the members of the regional political parties are also responsible for losing their popularity among the masses.

Manipur People Party (MPP), of course, can not extend its influence in the hill districts of the state. Therefore, the party has lost strength among the elected members. This might be due to inexperienced leaders of the party. As a regional party of the state. In fact, socialist minded hill people did not trust the regional political parties. The rise of MPP reflected the broader trend of regionalism in Indian politics. In short, local parties emerged to champion state-specific issues that were neglected by national parties. However, regional political parties of the state have failed to become the custodians of Manipur's people.

Indian National Congress (INC) was the most powerful and influential national political party, and it had hereditary-like party politics at its centre. It had swallowed almost all regional political parties in North East India; the INC had not escaped from national dominance politics. while politicians of the North East state have inclined more towards personal interest, even some politician do not have their own national feeling to save and encourage regional development and social upliftment. Almost all the political leaders have been devoted only to personal interest and benefits.

In Manipur, Most of the elected members do not possess common sense and societal interest. Generally, they look for their own benefits. Even if parties become the ruling party, then the members of the party tend to seek power by attempting to become members of the cabinet ministers in the government. The people of Manipur felt disappointed with the party because it failed to address the causes and political aspirations that were included in the party's ideology and manifestos during the time of the election. On the other hand, a national party, the BJP, began to hijack and suppress all issues and the rights of the indigenous people, regional parties' ideologies and feelings.

Manipur regional parties failed to effectively tackle insurgency and ethnic violence in the state and other issues, such as border issues, illegal immigrants, and kuki narcoterrorism emanating from Myanmar, erstwhile Burma, further erode public trust. The shift away from MPP from regional political aspiration, original political agendas in pursuit of electoral gain, alienated many Manipuri nationalists and core supporters of the party.

INABILITY TO GOVERN EFFECTIVELY;

Manipur People's Party (MPP) the party formed government for the three times. Md Alimudin was the first chief minister from MPP, Rajkumar Ranbir Singh was the second Chief minister from MPP for the period from 23RD February, 1990 to 6TH January 1992.

One of the major issues of the regional political party for losing its popularity in Manipur was the allegation and involvement in corruption. Indeed, the MPP government faced widespread allegations of corruption during its two-term rule, which severely damaged its credibility among the voters and among the local masses.

The inexperienced leaders, financial crisis, rise of educated unemployment, inability to pay salaries to its employees during the rule of MPP, led to the development of a perception of anti-employee employees and ineffectiveness in governance, which led to a fall in its trust. Corruption and instability during the MPP rule had a direct and significant negative impact on its popularity among the people. However, the party had come to power on a strong anti-corruption stance and platform, promising to cleanse the state.

MPP ministers were seen for misusing power and engaging in the same corrupt practices that they had promised to eliminate from the state. This led to widespread public disappointment and anger, steady erosion of MPP's core principles, primary supports and bases.

Regional political parties of the state were not formed purely on the basis of regional issues and sentiments. Manipur People's Party lost its identity as one of the strongest regional political parties in Manipur. Due to its alliance, from time to time, with national parties like INC and other national parties, MPP was hoping to retain some relevance and influence in state governance. But, this alliance, however, has led to the eruption of criticism that MPP has compromised on its core principles, as national political parties' policies and manifestos sometimes have contradictions with the regional aspirations of the people of the state, and nationalist sentiments. This contradiction creates a confusion state and thus, the elected persons from the regional political party did not have a clear roadmap and could not decide what was to be done for the state decisively.

In brief, Regional political party inability to effectively address all the major and emerging issues like economic development, social development, rights of the indigenous people, problems of insurgency, issues of unemployment, ethnic conflicts, and illegal immigration etc. led to the reduction of voter's trust over the party and also further tarnished regional political party image and subsequently led to the loss of public support and confidence.

ELECTORAL SETBACKS;

Regional party dominance in Manipur politics, which started diminishing from the 2002 election, marked a sharp decay in regional politics as the party lost power to national political parties. However, Congress, amid allegations of misgovernance, misuse of power and corruption, has run the state government successively for fifteen years. After that, in all subsequent elections, from local bodies to general elections, they witnessed a steady decrease in the voter share and seats in the state legislative assembly elections. It can be empirically shown from the fact that in the 2022 state legislative general assembly, local regional political parties such as Naga People's Front (NPF) and Kuki People's Alliance (KPA) people won five and two seats respectively, MPP could not secure a single seat. (<https://results.eci.gov.in>) This shows the replacement of MPP with NPF and KPA, the sharp decline of MPP, which once formed the government and influenced the electoral politics of Manipur.

To sum up, Manipur People Party (MPP) has failed to live up to people's expectations and its failed to deliver on its promises; loss of credibility and trust was a key factor in the party's declining popularity and electoral setbacks in the subsequent years. These factors combined to produce a steady decline in the Manipur People's Party's electoral fortunes and political relevance in regional politics.

In another account, a regional political party called Manipur State Congress Party (MSCP) was formed in 1997 with some legislators defected from the then ruling Indian National Congress (INC). It was led by W. Nipamacha Singh and formed a coalition government. Even the party could make Thounaojam Chaoba Singh a Member of Parliament of the Inner Manipur Parliamentary constituency and becoming a Union Minister of State for food processing during Atal Behari Vajpayee's government. However, MSCP got submerged as there was an internal feud within the party and the subsequent debacle it faced in the subsequent election. Finally, it was merged with the Indian National Congress in 2014. Thus, from the above facts, it can be concluded that regional political parties do not subscribe to the strong regional political aspirations, ideologies and the pulse of the people rather it was flouted and ended based on the electoral circumstances and personal gains of the politician. The alliance with the national political parties poses strong questions about their foundational principles.

DECLINE OF THE INC

The Congress Party was one of the strongest political parties with presence and support in every part of Manipur and North East India. It dominated the politics of the state for decades since Indian independence. However, it started declining with the rise of regional political parties such as MPP, MSCP, Federal Party of Manipur (FPM), coupled with the problems of internal dissension, defection of prominent leaders of INC to BJP before the 11th state legislative assembly election of 2017. Besides, the significant decline on the part of the Congress party occurred when N. Biren Singh, the former member of the cabinet minister of the then Congress government under the Chief ministership of O. Ibobi Singh, holding the post of cabinet minister of irrigation and flood control and youth affairs and sports, defected from Congress and joined the BJP in 2016. Similarly, defection of Govindas Konthoujam from Congress, resigning from the post of INC President and joining BJP in 2021, and ultimately becoming a cabinet minister in N. Biren Singh government, further diminished the image of INC. Besides, the serious allegation of fake encounters during O. Ibobi's Congress government, and a few notorious events of fake encounters of Thangjam Manorama in 2004 and Chungkham Shanjit fake encounter in 2009 can be mentioned. (<https://www.bbc.com>, published on 2nd July 2017), Further, the problems of Inner Line Permit issues (ILP) and frequent blocking of national highways, for instance, an economic blockade called by UNC for 130 days, blocking the supply of essential commodities and items in national highways of Manipur (<https://indianexpress.com> published on 19th March 2017). This resulted in the loss of people's trust in INC. Moreover, 15 years under the Congress government led people to think of flavouring the test new political parties. This significantly boosts and lends

opportunity to the newly arrived saffron party to dominate politics of Manipur. N. Biren Singh government was instrumental in expanding the BJP's influence across the state.

RISE OF THE BJP IN NORTH EASTERN POLITICS

BJP, which was a marginal party and had non-presence status in Assam, Manipur and Tripura politics until the early 1980's and assembly elections changed drastically, and the shift in the party's trajectory in the north is witnessed after the coming of the BJP government in Assam in 2016 with Sarbananda Sonowal as Chief Minister, a BJP-led coalition government under N. Biren Singh in Manipur in 2017, and the BJP government in Tripura under the chief ministership of Biplab Kumar Deb. The ascendancy of the BJP in these three states of north east states boosted the expansion and consolidation of the party holds in the region.

As far as Manipur electoral politics is concerned, the BJP began to contest elections from the 1984 state legislative assembly, but began to win, i.e one seat in the state legislative election held in 1995. And it could not win a single seat in election held in 2007 and 2012 general elections. But in the case of the Lok Sabha election, It could start to win only in 2019 Lok Sabha Election. Thus, It can be concluded that there is a paradigm shift from regional political parties and Indian National Congress (INC) dominance in Manipur and to the saffron national party called BJP. The party continued its strong performance in the subsequent election held in 2017 and 2022.

Regarding the state general assembly held in 2022, the BJP swept the election and got an absolute majority as 32 BJP MLAs out of 60 MLAs won the election, which makes the BJP the second National non-Congress political party which retain power after Janata Dal formed a government in 1979. Now, the BJP has established itself as the dominant political force in the states.

BJP successfully combined its national ideological agenda (Hindutva, rightist nationalism) with regional issues such as trans border illegal immigration issues, ethnic identity and developments. Thus, the party projected and propelled itself as a party that could ensure both regional security and national integration. While regionalism demands the BJP's brand of nationalism, which, combined with promises to protect indigenous rights, attracted a broad spectrum of voters. In fact, the BJP capitalised on anti-immigrant sentiments, promising to protect the indigenous people's right of Manipur and preserving its distinct identity. The NRC (National Register of Citizens) and CAA (Citizenship Amendment Act) debates and discussions held in a controversial manner led to the mobilisation and polarisation that benefited the BJP in consolidating Hindu voters in Manipur and North East India.

But as far as hill districts of Manipur are concerned, the BJP could produce a larger number of elected representatives in the 12th state legislative assembly election as compared to the earlier general election. The signing of the Framework Agreement between the Indian government and NSCN (IM) in 2015 placated the voters from the Naga community. On the other hand, the hope and aspiration of autonomy and separate administration in the Kuki Kuki-dominated area and its realisation when the BJP government came to power, led to the election of BJP candidates in the State legislative election from Kuki-dominated areas.

Another responsible factor for the rise of BJP was, now many younger voters were less attached to the memories and sentiments of the North Eastern region requires and are more attracted to BJP's promises and protection of territorial integrity, preserving the rights of the indigenous people of Manipur jobs, infrastructure development, agenda and protection of national integration (<https://aninews.in> published on 17 February,2022). With the rise of national political parties, MPP's traditional support base has fragmented, with maximum supporters fleeing to the BJP and other political parties such as INC, NPP, few other newer regional political parties such as NPF, KPA etc.

CONCLUSION;

The Election Commission of India (ECI) derecognised the Manipur People's Party in 2013. It is said that the main reason for derecognising the party, which had ruled the state for more than two terms, was that none of its candidates had won the last state assembly election in 2012 and Lok Sabha election in 2009. Manipur People's Party can not extend its organisational structure in the hill district of Manipur. It failed to produce a candidate in the hill areas in the state general assembly Election. This makes the party valley-based based confining its area of influence in the valley region. Even in the election of municipality and Panchayati Raj, it failed to produce elected representatives from its party. One of the main factors for facing a debacle in the election by MPP was a weak financial base, as a consequence, it could not ensure funding to the candidates, which is crucial for political mobilisation. Secondly, deviation from regional political ideology, giving emphasis on personal interest among the leaders of the party, and frequent defections are the responsible factors for the submergence of regional political parties of Manipur. The return of the regional political party requires reemphasising the rebuilding of much eroded public trust and beliefs of the people through the mobilisation of political ideas and regional political aspirations. Secondly, the level of dedication and devotion among the party leaders, shunning individual interests and personal gains, must be ensured. Thirdly, the expansion of political activities vertically and horizontally, with a futuristic regional political outlook, is also an indispensable

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